

Numerical simulation for frequency dependence of fatigue failure for polymer and polymer composite

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Frequency Dependence of Fatigue Failure

Experimental results of fatigue test for the same specimen, amplitude of load and stress ratio, but different frequency.

Damage progress for one cycle becomes remarkable due to viscoelastic nature.
 →Less cyclic loadings

Damage progress is accelerated by **elevated temperature** due to heat generation caused by such as friction inside specimen.
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Objective

Experimental results of fatigue test for the same specimen, amplitude of load and stress ratio, but different frequency.

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We need to evaluate the durability by considering both viscoelastic damage progress and damage acceleration by temperature elevation.

Our previously developed **entropy-based damage criterion** (Koyanagi et al. International Journal of Fatigue 2022, and Kudo et al. Polymers 2025) is capable of simulating viscoelastic damage progression and the reduction in fatigue life at lower frequencies. Moreover, the model incorporates heat generation during cyclic loading and captures the accelerated damage behavior due to temperature rise.

In this presentation, we introduce our **simulation results based on this model**.

Koyanagi et al. International Journal of Fatigue 2022

→ Degradation before damage onset
 → Degradation after damage onset

- Based on Hashin's law.
- The material strength can degrade with entropy generation (\cong Dissipated energy).
- The fracture energy also degrades with entropy generation.
- **Dissipated energy** is calculated considering orthotropic viscoelastic relationship and stress strain history.

Deng et al. Materials 2023

Definitions of Strength Reduction, Fracture Energy Reduction, and Failure Judgement

Strength reduction

$$\begin{aligned}X_T^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_{ft}} s_{n0}) X_T^0, & X_C^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_{fc}} s_{n0}) X_C^0, \\Y_T^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_m} s_{n0}) Y_T^0, & Y_C^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_{fc}} s_{n0}) Y_C^0, \\S_{12}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_m} s_{n0}) S_{12}^0, & S_{13}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_m} s_{n0}) S_{13}^0, \\S_{23}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_m} s_{n0}) S_{23}^0\end{aligned}$$

Fracture energy reduction

$$\begin{aligned}G_{ft}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_{fc}} s_{n0})^2 G_{ft}^0, & G_{fc}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_{fc}} s_{n0})^2 G_{fc}^0, \\G_{mt}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_m} s_{n0})^2 G_{mt}^0, & G_{mc}^* &= (1 - \underline{\alpha_m} s_{n0})^2 G_{mc}^0\end{aligned}$$

Failure judgement

$$e_{ft} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T^*} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}^*} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}^*} \right)^2$$

$$e_{fc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C^*} \right)^2$$

$$e_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_T^*} \right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{(S_{23}^*)^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{(S_{12}^*)^2} + \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{(S_{13}^*)^2}$$

$$e_{mc} = \left[\left(\frac{Y_C^*}{2S_{23}^*} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_C^*} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23}^*} \right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{(S_{23}^*)^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{(S_{12}^*)^2} + \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{(S_{13}^*)^2}$$

α can be determined based on micromechanical analysis (Sekino et al. Journal of Composite Science 2024). In this presentation we use tentative values for the purpose of qualitative simulations.

We can numerically simulate:

- ❑ **Frequency dependence** on fatigue failure and damage progression
- ❑ **Stress ratio effects** on fatigue life and damage evolution
- ❑ Fatigue behavior under **variable amplitude loading**, including random or spectrum loading
- ❑ Universal prediction of fatigue failure **and residual strength** under arbitrary loading histories
- ❑ Fatigue behavior under **thermal cyclic loadings**.
- ❑ Detailed analysis of **damage initiation and evolution** during various fatigues.

Therefore, this model serves as a universally applicable tool for discussing the long-term durability of composite materials.

We develop viscoelastic-plastic model.

We assume a part of strain increment is assigned as plastic deformation.

The energy dissipated through damping and plastic deformation is assumed to be converted into heat.

Heat transfer to the outside of the specimen is also considered. When internal heat generation exceeds the rate of heat dissipation, such as under high-frequency cyclic loading, the **specimen temperature increases**.

This temperature rise accelerates damage progression through the **time-temperature superposition principle**, which effectively speeds up the time scale of material behavior.

The accelerated time scale increases energy dissipation, **resulting in a reduced number of cycles to failure at high frequencies**.

◆ Plastic strain

$$\Delta \varepsilon^{nr}(i) = \left(a \times \sigma(i)^c \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\sigma(i)}{\sigma_0} \right)^d \right) + b \left(1 - \exp \left(- \left(\frac{\sigma(i)}{\sigma_0} \right)^d \right) \right) \right) \times \Delta \varepsilon(i)$$

◆ Surface thermal conduction

$$Q = Ah(T_{el} - T_{atm})$$

◆ Heat transfer inside materials

$$c\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \lambda_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \lambda_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \lambda_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \alpha_d \frac{\partial E_{dis}}{\partial t}$$

◆ Dissipating energy

$$E_{dis} = \sigma_n : \Delta \varepsilon_v + \sigma_n : \Delta \varepsilon^{nr}$$

◆ Time-temperature superposition principle

$$\log \alpha^{TR}(T^{test}) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T^{test}} - \frac{1}{T^{ref}} \right)$$

Numerical Conditions

Figure 2. Flowchart of process used for updating stress and entropy.

Table 5. Thermal parameters.

Parameter	Value
Specific heat c	844 J/(kg·K)
Density ρ	1550 kg/m ³
Surface heat transfer coefficient h	20 W/(m ² ·K)
Axial thermal conductivity λ_x	5.47 W/(m·K)
Transverse thermal conductivity λ_y, λ_z	0.358 W/(m·K)

Table 2. Material properties, including those of Maxwell elements.

Elastic Modulus (MPa)	$n=1$	$n=2$	$n=3$	$n=4$	$n=5$
E_{11}^n	128,000	80	80	80	80
E_{22}^n, E_{33}^n	4290	267	267	267	267
G_{12}^n, G_{13}^n	1810	133	133	133	133
G_{23}^n	1610	101	101	101	101
Viscosity (MPa·s)	$n=1$	$n=2$	$n=3$	$n=4$	$n=5$
η_{11}^n	6.00×10^{30}	3.50×10^6	3.00×10^6	3.00×10^5	6.00×10^3
η_{22}^n, η_{33}^n	6.00×10^{30}	1.17×10^7	1.00×10^7	1.00×10^6	2.01×10^4
η_{12}^n, η_{13}^n	6.00×10^{30}	5.83×10^6	5.00×10^6	5.00×10^5	9.99×10^3
η_{23}^n	6.00×10^{30}	4.45×10^6	3.81×10^6	3.81×10^5	7.63×10^3

Table 3. Strength and degradation properties for Hashin's damage criterion.

Material Properties	Value
Initial axial tensile strength $X_{T,0}$	3930 MPa
Initial axial compressive strength $X_{C,0}$	2775 MPa
Initial transverse tensile strength $Y_{T,0}$	150 MPa
Initial transverse compressive strength $Y_{C,0}$	270 MPa
Initial axial shear strength $S_{12,0}, S_{13,0}$	117 MPa
Initial axial transverse strength $S_{23,0}$	117 MPa
Initial fiber directional tensile fracture energy *	12 N/mm
Initial fiber directional compressive fracture energy *	6 N/mm
Initial transverse tensile fracture energy *	0.42 N/mm
Initial transverse compressive fracture energy *	1.36 N/mm
Degradation coefficient $\alpha(\alpha_{AT}, \alpha_{AC}, \alpha_{A0})$	3000 K·mm ³ /J
Time acceleration factor α_d	30

* Descriptions of these parameters are omitted in this paper to avoid an overly long explanation: please see ref. [21].

Numerical Simulation Results; One Element Analysis

Cyclic displacement of 0-1% uniaxial tension in 22 (90°) direction

<Boundary conditions

Symmetry

(ADHE, ABCD, DCGH)

Surface Heat Conduction
(ABFE, BCGF, EFGH)

<Load control

Cyclic loading(EFGH)

Frequency : 0.1Hz, 0.25Hz, 0.5Hz, 1Hz,
2Hz, 4Hz, 5Hz, 6.25Hz, 8Hz, 10Hz

Simulate fatigue failure by Abaqus 2020

Stress is calculated using a user-subroutine UMAT

Results for CFRP; One Element Analysis, 1% Cyclic Strain in 22 Direction

- ◆ The CFRP fatigue failure simulations exhibit the same trend as the experimental results.
- ◆ The number of cycles to fatigue failure initially increases with rising frequency, but then decreases at higher frequencies. The initial increase is attributed to reduced viscoelastic damage per cycle, while the subsequent decrease is due to temperature rise within the specimen, which accelerates damage progression.
- ◆ These results imply that evaluating the durability of CFRP is highly complex, and that it is difficult to determine fatigue life based on a limited number of tests.

Cross-ply Laminates Modeled with Element-Specific Strengths

Figure 3. Geometric model of cross-ply CFRP laminate. (a) Boundary conditions, (b) Elements representing materials used in the simulation (green color represents the material for the 0° ply, and the other colors indicate the materials in the 90° ply).

Individual elements degrade under cyclic loading, and typical patterns of fatigue damage observed in experiments can also be reproduced through numerical simulations.

The temperature rise effect is included in previous results.

Numerical Results for 6.25Hz Fatigue Damage Simulation

Numerical Results for 5Hz Fatigue Damage Simulation

Summarized Numerical Results

Figure 9. Number of cycles observed before formation of three transverse cracks versus loading frequency.

Experimental results:
Crack density vs
frequency

Figure 10. Relationship between the crack density at 10^5 cycles and loading frequency, from experiments.

Low frequency

Intermediate frequency

High frequency

Figure 8. The progression of the transverse cracks (left) and temperature distribution (right) in the 90° ply after 200 cycles under a loading frequency of (a) 0.1 Hz, (b) 2 Hz, and (c) 6.25 Hz.

Summary

- An entropy-based viscoelastic-plastic model was developed to simulate fatigue failure of polymer materials and CFRP under various frequencies.
- The model incorporates internal heat generation and time–temperature superposition, capturing the bell-shaped frequency dependence of fatigue life.
- Numerical results show good agreement with experimental trends, including temperature-driven damage acceleration.
- Element-wise modeling was used to simulate cross-ply laminates, demonstrating localized damage evolution and strength degradation.
- The model provides a versatile tool for durability prediction under various loading conditions and supports the design of reliable composite structures.

